

Graduale Ilmolense: Inventory of Chants

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Introduction

This inventory catalogues the liturgical contents of the sixteenth-century paper gradual known as *Graduale Ilmolense*, now divided between two bindings housed at the National Library of Finland (MSS A.ö.II.55 & A.ö.II.29). Proceeding from the first folio to the last as currently bound, the inventory assigns each chant an ID number, genre, mode, and incipit. The ID numbers and incipits follow the usage of Cantus Database and Cantus Index.¹

With its focus on liturgical contents, this inventory does not examine codicological features. These have been thoroughly described by Jesse Keskiäho in the catalogue of the *Codices Fennici* Database.²

Brief Description

Shelfmark: Helsinki, National Library of Finland, MSS A.ö.II.55 & A.ö.II.29.

Dating: Saec. XVI^{2/3}

Origin and provenance: At least partially copied in the Birgittine house of Naantali. Probably later used in the Ilmajoki Church, in the historical province of Ostrobothnia.

Graduale Ilmolense consists of three parts:

Part I (ff. 1r–131v), written in Latin, contains the proper chants of the *Temporale* and *Sanctorale*. This part, which concludes with the Marian chant *Alleluia Virga Jesse floruit virgo*, was never completed (the leaves with initially empty staves at the end of the section were later filled with vernacular chants and now constitute the second part). Although the first part is generally well preserved, it lacks folios from the very beginning of the *Temporale* section. Six of these missing folios (five complete and the upper inner corner of the sixth) are now bound – in reverse order – at the beginning of another manuscript, Helsinki, National Library of Finland, A.ö.II.29 (known as *Antiphonarium Ilmolense*). Due to the absence of modern pagination, these leaves are designated with letters A–E in this inventory.

Part II (ff. 132r–140v), written in Swedish and Finnish, is a fragment of a Lutheran gradual. It contains two Swedish sequences (ff. 132r–134r), Swedish ordinarium chants of the Mass (ff. 135r–140v) and the beginning of the Finnish sequence *Pyhän hengen armo olcon* (Lat. Sancti Spiritus assit, ff. 140r–v).

Part III (ff. 141r–194v), written in Latin, contains the *Kyriale* and *Sequentiary* sections: the ordinarium chants of the Mass (ff. 141r–150v) and 40 sequences (ff. 151r–194v).

¹ <https://cantusdatabase.org/>; <https://cantusindex.org/>.

² Seek the *Codices Fennici* database, <https://www.codicesfennici.fi/>, under ‘Helsinki, National Library, A.ö.II.55 + A.ö.II.29. “Graduale Ilmolense”’. The database does not assign permanent identifiers for individual manuscripts.

Notes on the Inventory

Brackets are employed to signify content that was omitted or has gone missing from the manuscript. That may include, for instance, feast markings or the initial words missing from a fragmentary chant. To aid navigation, the original sequence of the chants in the *Antiphonarium Ilmolense* (A.ö.II.29) section has also been indicated in brackets.

All the feast rubrics are catalogued in accordance with the terminology of Cantus Index (<https://cantusindex.org/>). In cases where the rubric conflicts with that of the Cantus Index, the rubric of the manuscript is given in the footnotes. A significant area of divergence occurs during the post-Pentecost period, since the *Graduale Ilmolense* numbers the Sundays from the feast of the Holy Trinity, whereas the Cantus Index calculates them from Pentecost on. To give an example, the manuscript reading *Dominica prima post Festum sancte trinitatis* is given in the footnotes, while the feast is indexed as *Dominica 2 post Pentecost*.

Each chant is identified by Cantus ID number, genre, mode, and the incipit as spelled in the Cantus Index. Since the Cantus Index provides an identification by the ordinarium chant text rather than by its melody, the inventory follows a different identification system in the *Kyriale* section (where several melodies are provided for each text). The chants in the *Kyriale* are classified using both the Cantus ID number and the designation established in the systems of Landwehr-Melnick (mMELO), Bosse (mBOS), Thannabaur (mTHA) and Schildbach (mSCB).³ In the manuscript, the *Kyriale* chants have been left unrubricated. To indicate the ordinarium melody combinations, Ermo Äikää's categorizations for Kyrie–Gloria–Sanctus–Agnus Dei combinations (OM-series) are given in square brackets.⁴

Chants for which the manuscript provides only the incipit are marked with an asterisk [*].

³ See Hiley 1993, 148.

⁴ Äikää 1995, 35–37, 40–41, 65–82, 205–219, 330.

Abbreviations

A	Antiphon
Al	Alleluia
AlV	Alleluia verse
BD	Benedicamus domino
Cm	Communion
f.	foli
fols.	folios
Gl	Gloria
Gr	Gradual
GrV	Graduale verse
In	Introit
InV	Introit verse
Ite	Ite missa est
Ky	Kyrie
MA	Missae Aboense
Of	Offertory
Sa	Sanctus
Sq	Sequence
Tc	Tract
TcV	Tract verse

Inventory of Chants

Proprium de tempore

A.ö.II.29, (fols. A–F):

LACUNA

Ar

[Nativitas Domini]

[g00554 Gr 5 Viderunt omnes fines terrae salutare De-]i nostri
g00554a GrV 5 Notum fecit dominus salutare suum⁵
g00556 Al 2 Alleluia Dies sanctificatus illuxit nobis⁶

Av

g00557 Of 4 Tui sunt caeli et tua⁷
g00558 Cm 1 Viderunt omnes fines terrae salutare⁸ [-> *Dum medium silentium*, f. Er]

Br

[Dom. 1 p. Epiphaniam]

[g00613 In 8 In excelso throno vidi sedere]
g00613b InV 8 [Jubilate deo omnis terra servite... Domino] in laetitiae.
g00614 Gr 7 Benedictus dominus deus Israel
g00614a GrV 7 Suscipiant montes pacem populo tuo

Bv

g00616 Al 3 Alleluia Jubilate deo omnis terra
g00617 Of 5 Jubilate deo omnis terra servite
g00618 Cm 1 Fili quid [fecisti nobis sic...]

Cr

[Epiphania]

g00599 Al 2 Alleluia Vidimus stellam ejus in
g00600 Of 5 Reges Tharsis et insulae munera

Cv

g00601 Cm 3 Vidimus stellam ejus in oriente

Dom. 1 p. Epiphaniam⁹

g00613 In 8 In excelso throno vidi sedere
g00613b InV 8 Jubilate deo omnis terra servite domino [in laetitia.] [-> *In excelso*, f. Br]

Dr

Circumcisio Domini

In Puer natus est nobis*
Gr Viderunt omnes*
g00585 Al 7 Alleluia Multifarie olim Deus loquens
Of Tui sunt caeli*
Cm Viderunt omnes*

Vigilia Epiphaniae

In Lux fulgebit*
Gr Benedictus qui venit*

⁵ Only partially visible.

⁶ Only partially visible.

⁷ Only partially visible.

⁸ Only partially visible.

⁹ Dominica infra octauam epiphaniae domini officium.

	Al			Alleluia Dominus regnavit*
	Of			Deus enim firmavit*
	Cm			[Tolle puerum*] ¹⁰
Epiphania ¹¹				
Dv	g00596	In	2	Ecce advenit dominator dominus et
	g00596a.1	InV	2	Deus iudicium tuum regi da
	g00597	Gr	5	Omnes de Saba venient aurum
	g00597a	GrV	5	Surge et illuminare Jerusalem quia [-> <i>Alleluia Vidimus</i> , f. Cr]
Er				
Dom. P. Nat. Dom. ¹²				
	g00578	In	8	Dum medium silentium tenerent omnia
	g00578a	InV	8	Dominus regnavit decorem indutus est
	g00579	Gr	2T	Speciosus forma prae filiis hominum
Ev				
	g00579a	GrV	2T	Eruclavit cor meum verbum bonum
	g00628	Al		Alleluia Dominus regnavit*
	g00629	Of		Deus enim firmavit*
	g00581	Cm	8	Tolle puerum et matrem ejus [-> <i>Puer natus*</i> f. Dr]

LACUNA

A^o II 55, (fols. 1r–194v):

1r				
				[Dom. 4 Quadragesimae]
	In	5		[Laetare Jerusalem et conventum facite] omnes qui...
	InV	5		Laetatus sum in his quae
	Gr	7		Laetatus sum in his quae
1v				
	GrV	7		Fiat pax in virtute tua
	Tr	8		Qui confidunt in domino sicut
	TrV	8		Montes in circuitu ejus et ¹³
2r				
	Of	2		Laudate dominum quia benignus est
	Cm	4		Jerusalem quae aedificatur ut civitas
2v				
				Dom. de Passione
	g00800	In	3	Judica me deus et discerne
	g00800c	InV	3	Emitte lucem tuam et veritatem
	g00801	Gr	3	Eripe me domine de inimicis
3r				
	g00801a	GrV	3	Liberator meus domine de gentibus
	g00803	Tc	8	Saepe expugnaverunt me a juventute

¹⁰ Only the communio rubric. The *Tolle puerum* incipit is missing.

¹¹ In die sancto officium.

¹² Dominica infra octauam natalis Domini officium.

¹³ Only partially visible.

3v				
	g00803a	TcV	8	Dicat nunc Israel saepe expugnaverunt
	g00803b	TcV	8	Etenim non potuerunt mihi supra
	g00803c	TcV	8	Prolongaverunt iniquitatem sibi dominus Justus
4r				
	g00807	Of	1	Confitebor tibi domine in toto
	g00808	Cm	8	Hoc corpus quod pro vobis
4v				
Dom. in Palmis ¹⁴				
	g00845	In	8	Domine ne longe facias auxilium
	g00845c	InV	8	Deus deus meus respice in
	g00846	Gr	4	Tenuisti manum dexteram meam in
5r				
	g00846a	GrV	4	Quam bonus Israel deus rectis
5v				
	g00848	Tc	2	Deus deus meus respice in me
	g00848a	TcV	2	Longe a salute mea verba
	g00848b	TcV	2	Deus meus clamabo per diem
6r				
	g00848c	TcV	2	Tu autem in sancto habitas
	g00848d	TcV	2	In te speraverunt patres nostril
	g00848e	TcV	2	Ad te clamaverunt et salvi
	g00848f	TcV	2	Ego autem sum vermis et
6v				
	g00848g	TcV	2	Omnes qui videbant me aspernabantur
	g00848h	TcV	2	Speravit in domino eripiat eum
	g00848i	TcV	2	Ipsi vero consideraverunt et conspexerunt
7r				
	g00848j	TcV	2	Libera me de ore leonis
	g00848k	TcV	2	Qui timetis dominum laudate eum
	g00848l	TcV	2	Annuntiabitur domino generatio ventura et
7v				
	g00848m	TcV	2	Populo qui nascetur quem fecit
	g00862	Of	8	Improperium exspectavit cor meum et
8r				
	g00863	Cm	8	Pater si non potest hic
Fer. 5 Maj. Hebd. ¹⁵				
	g00180	In	4	Nos autem gloriari oportet in
8v				
	g00180b	InV	4	Deus misereatur nostri et benedicat
	505005	Gr	5	Christus factus est pro nobis
	505005a	GrV	5	Propter quod et deus exaltavit

LACUNA

[Sabbato Sancto]

9r

005371 A 8 Vespere autem sabbati quae lucescit (ad Magnif.)

¹⁴ Dominica ramis palmarum.

¹⁵ Feria quinta in cena domini officium.

Dom. Resurrectionis¹⁶

	g01007	In	4	Resurrexi et adhuc tecum sum
	g01007a	InV	4	Domine probasti me et cognovisti
9v				
	008414	Gr	2T	Haec dies quam fecit dominus
	008414a	GrV	2T	Confitemini domino quoniam bonus
	008435	Al	7	Alleluia Pascha nostrum immolatus est
10r				
	g01012	Of	4	Terra tremuit et quievit dum
	g01013	Cm	6	Pascha nostrum immolatus est Christus
10v				
Fer. 2 p. Pascha				
	g01014	In	8	Introduxit vos dominus in terram
	g01014d	InV	8	Confitemini domino quoniam bonus quoniam
	008414	Gr		Haec dies quam*
	008414b	GrV	2T	Dicat nunc Israel quoniam bonus
11r				
	507021	Al	1	Alleluia Nonne cor nostrum ardens
	g01018	Of	8	Angelus domini descendit de caelo
11v				
	g01019	Cm	6T	Surrexit dominus et apparuit Petro
Fer. 3 p. Pascha				
	g01020	In	7	Aqua sapientiae potavit eos alleluia
	g01020b	InV	7	Confitemini domino quoniam bonus quoniam
12r				
	008414	Gr		Haec dies quam*
	008414c	GrV	2T	Dicant nunc qui redempti sunt
	008439	Al	1	Alleluia Surrexit dominus
12v				
	g01024	Of	4	Intonuit de caelo dominus et
	g01025	Cm	7	Si consurrexistis cum Christo quae
13r				
Fer. 4 p. Pascha				
	g01026	In	7	Venite benedicti patris mei percipite
	g01026d	InV	7	Confitemini domino quoniam bonus
	008414	Gr		Haec dies quam*
	008414d	GrV	2	Dextera domini fecit virtutem dextera
	507009	Al	1	Alleluia Christus resurgens ex mortuis
	g01030	Of	8	Portas caeli aperuit dominus et ... illis manna [panem ...]

LACUNA [?]

14r

Octava Paschae

	g01049	In	6T	Quasi modo geniti infantes alleluia
	g01049c	InV	6T	Exsultate deo adiutori nostro
	g01051	Al	7	Alleluia Post dies octo januis
	g01023	Al	1	Alleluia Surrexit dominus de sepulcro

¹⁶ In die sancto pasche officium.

14v				
	g01018	Of		Angelus Domini*
	g01052	Cm		Mitte manum*
	Require de sancto thoma apostolo.			
	Dom. 2 p. Pascha ¹⁷			
	g01053	In	4	Misericordia domini plena est terra
	g01305b	InV	4	Exsultate justi in domino rectos
	g01055	Al	1	Alleluia Ego sum pastor bonus
15r				
	g02085	Al	1	Alleluia Surrexit christus et illuxit
	g01056	Of	2	Deus deus meus ad te
15v				
	g01057	Cm	8	Ego sum pastor bonus alleluia
	Dom. 3.p. Pascha			
	g01058	In	8	Jubilate deo omnis terra alleluia
	g01058a	InV	8	Dicite deo quam terribilia sunt
16r				
	g02601	Al	8	Alleluia Modicum et non videbitis
	g02080	Al	3	Alleluia Surrexit pastor bonus qui
16v				
	g01061	Of	4	Lauda anima mea dominum laudabo
	g01062	Cm	8	Modicum et non videbitis me
17r				
	Dom. 4.p. Pascha			
	g01063	In	6	Cantate domino canticum novum alleluia
	g01063a	InV	6	Salvabit sibi dextera ejus
	g02174.1	Al	1	Alleluia Vado ad eum qui
17v				
	g01023	Al		Alleluia Surrexit dominus*
	g00623	Of		Jubilate deo universa*
	g01066	Cm	8	Cum venerit paraclitus spiritus veritatis
	Dom. 5 p. Pascha			
	g02089	In	3	Vocem jucunditatis annuntiate et audiatur
18r				
	g02089a	InV	3	Jubilate deo omnis terra psalmum
	g02177	Al	4	Alleluia Usque modo non petistis
	g02171	Al		Alleluia Surrexit Christus*
	g01070	Of		Benedicite gentes*
	g00335	Of		Confessio* ¹⁸
18v				
	g01071	Cm	1	Cantate domino alleluia cantate domino
	Fer. 2 in Letaniis			
	002822	A	2	Exsurge domine adjuva nos et
	002822b	AV	2	Deus auribus nostris audivimus patres
	g01075	In	4	Exaudivit de templo sancto suo

¹⁷ Dominica 1 post oct. pascha.

¹⁸ The rightmost rubric “Co” refers to the communion chant on the verso side. The exceptional rubric reading “R[esponsum]: immediate post offertorium de sancto laurencio Confessio” refers to the offertorium chant *Confessio et pulchritudine* sung on the feast of Laurent (f. 90v). The chant was likely sung as a response [!] to the first offertorium chant *Benedicite gentes*.

19r
g01075b InV 4 Diligam te domine fortitudo mea
507011 Al 8 Alleluia Confitemini domino quoniam bonus

19v
g01077 Of 6 Confitebor domino nimis in ore
g01078 Cm 1 Petite et accipietis quaerite et

20r
[Ascensionis Domini, in vigilia]
g01161 In 6 Omnes gentes plaudite manibus jubilate
g01161a InV 6 Subjecit populos nobis et gentes
g01069 Al 7 Alleluia Exivi a patre et

20v
g01082 Of 1 Ascendit deus in jubilatione
g01087 Cm 4 Pater cum essem cum eis

21r
Ascensio Domini¹⁹
g01079 In 7 Viri Galilaei quid admiramini aspicientes
g01079a InV 7 Cumque intuerentur in caelum euntem
g01080 Al 4 Alleluia Ascendit deus in jubilatione

21v
g02834 Al 1 Alleluia ascendens Christus in altum
g02180 Of 2 Viri Galilaei quid admiramini

22r
g01083 Cm 1 Psallite domino qui ascendit super

Dom. p. Ascensionem
g01084 In 1 Exaudi domine vocem meam

22v
g01155a InV 1 Dominus illuminatio mea et salus
g01080 Al Alleluia Ascendit deus*
g01081 Al 8 Alleluia Dominus in Sina in

23r
g01082 Of Ascendit deus*
g01087 Cm Pater cum essem*

In vigilia penthecosten lectio prima *Temptavit* [*Deus Abraham*].

Finita prima lectione immediate dicatur oratio *Deus qui in abrahe*.

Lectio ij *Scrripsit moyses*.

Post secundam lectionem cantetur tractus et cantentur versus alternati et similiter duorum sequentium tractuum.

Tractus.

Vigilia Pentecostes

g02373 Tc 8 Attende caelum et loquar et
g02373a TcV 8 Exspectetur sicut pluvia eloquium meum
g02373b TcV 8 Et sicut nix super foenum
g02373c TcV 8 Date magnificentia deo nostro deus

23v
g02373d TcV 8 Deus fidelis in quo non
Oratio Deus qui*
Lectio iij Apprehendent*

¹⁹ In die officium.

g02372	Tc		Vinea facta est*
Oratio			Deus qui nos*
Lectio iiij			Audi israhel*
Oratio			Deus incommutabilis
g02374	Tc		Sicut cervus*
Oratio			Concede*

Sequitur letania qua finita sacerdos dicat *Confiteor*. Dicat etiam orationem solitam ante altare Kyrieleyson. Gloria in excelsis.

	507011	Al		Alleluia Confitemini*
	g00715	Tc		Laudate dominum*
24r	g01088	Of	8	Emitte spiritum tuum et creabuntur
	g01089	Cm	5	Ultimo festivitatis die dicebat Jesus
Dom. Pentecostes				
24v	g01090	In	8	Spiritus domini replevit orbem terrarum
	g01090a.1	InV	8	Confirma hoc deus quod operates
	g01091	Al	4	Alleluia Emitte spiritum tuum et
	g01092	Al	2	Alleluia Veni sancte spiritus reple
	g01094	Of	4	Confirma hoc deus quod operates
	g01095	Cm	7	Factus est repente de caelo
25v	Fer. 2 Pent.			
	501001	In	2	Cibavit eos ex adipe frumenti
	501001a	InV	2	Exsultate deo adiutori nostro jubilate
26r	g02644	Al	2	Alleluia Spiritus sanctus procedens a throno
26v	g02103	Al	2	Alleluia Spiritus domini replevit orbem
	g01024	Of		Intonuit de caelo*
	g01098	Cm	8	Spiritus sanctus docebit vos alleluia
Fer. 3 Pent.				
	g02104	In	8	Accipite jocunditatem gloriae vestrae alleluia
	g02104a	InV	8	Attendite popule meus legem meam
27r	g01097	Al	1	Alleluia Loquebantur variis linguis apostoli
27v	507020	Al	1	Alleluia Non vos relinquam orphanos
	g01030	Of		Portas caeli*
	g01101	Cm	8	Spiritus qui a patre procedit
Fer. 4 Pent.				
	g01102	In	8	Deus dum egredereris coram populo
	g01102a	InV	8	Exsurgat deus et dissipentur inimici
		Al		Alleluia Spiritus domini*
28r	g03033	Al	1	Alleluia Factus est repente de
	g00726	Of		Meditabar*
	g01105	Cm	5	Pacem meam do vobis
De Trinitate				
	g01116	In	8	Benedicta sit sancta Trinitas atque

28v	g01116a.1	InV	8	Benedicamus patrem et filium cum
	g01117	Gr	5	Benedictus es domine qui intueris
	g01117a	GrV	5	Benedicite deum caeli quia fecit
	g01113	Al	8	Alleluia Benedictus es domine deus
29r	g01120	Of	3	Benedictus sit deus pater unigenitusque
	g01121	Cm	4	Benedicimus deum caeli et coram
29v	Corporis Christi			
	501001	In		Cibavit eos*
	g01127	Gr	7	Oculi omnium in te spirant
	g01127a	GrV	7	Aperis tu manum tuam et
30r	507001	Al	7	Alleluia Caro mea vere est
	g01030	Of		Portas caeli*
	g00808	Cm		Hoc corpus*
Dom. 2 p. Pent. ²⁰	g01122	In	5	Domine in tua misericordia speravi
30v	g01122a	InV	5	Usquequo domine oblivisceris me in
	g01123	Gr	5	Ego dixi domine miserere mei
	g01123a	GrV	5	Beatus qui intelligit super egenum
31r	g01125	Al	2	Alleluia Verba mea auribus percipe
	g00769	Of	5	Intende voci orationis meae rex
31v	g02185	Cm	2	Narrabo omnia mirabilia tua laetabor
Dom. 3 p. Pent.	g01133	In	1	Factus est dominus protector meus
	g01133a	InV	1	Diligam te domine virtus mea
32r	g01134	Gr	5	Ad dominum dum tribularer clamavi
	g01134a	GrV	6	Domine libera animam meam
	g02186	Al	8	Alleluia Deus iudex justus fortis
32v	g01137	Of	6	Domine convertere et eripe animam
Dom. 4 p. Pent.	g01145	In	6	Respice in me et miserere
	g01145b	InV	6	Ad te domine levavi animam
33r	g01146	Gr		Jacta cogitatum tuum in domino
	g01146a	GrV	7	Dum clamarem ad dominum exaudivit
33v	g02186	Al	5	Alleluia Diligam te domine virtus
	g01149	Of	3	Sperent in te omnes qui
34r	g01252	Cm	6	Ego clamavi quoniam exaudisti me

²⁰ Dominica prima post festum sancte trinitatis.

Dom. 5 p. Pent.				
34v	g01151	In	2	Dominus illuminatio mea et salus
	g01151b	InV	2	Si consistant adversus me castra
	g00707	Gr	5	Propitius esto domine peccatis nostris
35r				
	g00707a	GrV	5	Adjuva nos deus salutaris noster
	g01156	Al	6	Alleluia Domine in virtute tua
35v				
	g01153	Of	4	Illumina oculos meos nequando obdormiam
	g01154	Cm	2	Dominus firmamentum meum et refugium
36r				
Dom. 6 p. Pent.				
	g01155	In	4	Exaudi domine vocem meam qua
	g01155a	InV	4	Dominus illuminatio mea et salus
	g00709	Gr	5	Protector noster aspice deus et
36v				
	g00709a	GrV	6	Domine deus virtutum exaudi preces
	g01159	Al	3	Alleluia In te domine speravi
37r				
	g00731	Of	1	Benedicam dominum qui mihi tribuit
	g01157	Cm	7	Unam petii a domino hanc
Dom. 7 p. Pent.				
	g01158	In	2	Dominus fortitudo plebis suae et
	g01158a	InV	2	Ad te domine clamabo deus
	g00711	Gr	5	Convertere domine aliquantulum et
38r				
	g00711a	GrV	5	Domine refugium factus es nobis
	g01176	Al	2	Alleluia Eripe me de inimicis
	g00646	Of	4	Perfice gressus meos in semitis
38v				
	g01160	Cm	8	Circuibo et immolabo in tabernaculo
Dom. 9 p. Pent.				
39r	g01161	In	6	Omnes gentes plaudite manibus jubilate
	g01161a	InV	6	Subjecit populos nobis et gentes
	g01162	Gr	5	Venite filii audite me timorem
	g01162a	GrV	5	Accedite ad eum et illuminamini
	008440	Al	7	Alleluia Te decet hymnus deus
39v				
	g01165	Of	5	Sicut in holocaustum arietum et
	g01166	Cm	4	Inclina aurem tuam accelera ut
40r				
Dom. 9 p. Pent.				
	g01167	In	1	Suscepimus deus misericordiam tuam in
	g01167a	InV	1	Magnus dominus et laudabilis nimis
	g01168	Gr	5	Esto mihi in deum protectorem
40v				
	g01168a	GrV	5	Deus in te speravi domine
	g02191	Al	6	Alleluia Attendite popule meus in
	g01171	Of	5	Populum humilem salvum facies domine

41r					
	g01172	Cm	3	Gustate et videte quoniam suavis	
Dom. 10 p. Pent.					
	g01173	In	5	Ecce deus adjuvat me et	
41v					
	g01173a	InV	5	Deus in nomine tuo salvum	
	g01174	Gr	5	Domine dominus noster quam admirabile	
	g01174a	GrV	5	Quoniam elevata est magnificentia tua	
	g01554	Al	1	Alleluia Propitius esto domine peccatis	
42r					
	g00752	Of	6	Justitiae domini rectae laetificantes corda	
	g01205	Cm	8	Primum quaerite regnum dei et	
Dom. 11 p. Pent.					
	g01178	In	3	Dum clamarem ad dominum exaudivit	
42v					
	g01178b	InV	3	Exaudi deus orationem meam et ne despexeris	
	g01179	Gr	1	Custodi me domine ut pupillam	
43r					
	g01179a	GrV	1	De vultu tuo iudicium meum	
	g01186.1	Al	7	Alleluia Exsultate deo adjutori nostro	
43v					
	g00493	Of		Ad te domine levavi*	
	g01182	Cm	4	Acceptabis sacrificium iustitiae oblationes et	
Dom. 12 p. Pent.					
	g01183	In	5	Deus in loco sancto suo	
	g01183a	InV	5	Exsurgat deus et dissipentur inimici	
44r					
	g01184	Gr	6	In deo speravit cor meum	
	g01184a	GrV	5	Ad te domine clamavi deus	
	g01191	Al	3	Alleluia Domine deus salutis meae	
44v					
	g00668	Of	2T	Exaltabo te domine quoniam suscepisti	
	g01187	Cm	6	Honora dominum de tua substantia	
45r					
Dom. 13 p. Pent.					
	g02026	In	7	Deus in adiutorium meum intende	
	g02026a.1	InV	7	Avertantur retrorsum et erubescant qui	
	g01189	Gr	7	Benedicam dominum in omni tempore	
45v					
	g01189a	GrV	7	In domino laudabitur anima mea	
	g01197	Al	7	Alleluia Domine refugium factus es	
46r					
	g01192	Of	8	Precatus est Moyses in conspectus	
46v					
	g01193	Cm	1	De fructu operum tuorum domine	
Dom. 14 p. Pent.					
	g01193	In	7	Respice domine in testamentum tuum	
	g01194a	InV	7	Ut quid deus repulisti in	
47r					
	g01195	Gr	5	Respice domine in testamentum tuum	
	g01195a	GrV	5	Exsurge domine et iudica causam	

47v	g01203	Al	7	Alleluia Venite exsultemus domino
	g01198	Of	2	In te speravi domine dixi
	g01199	Cm	5	Panem de caelo dedisti nobis
Dom. 15 p. Pent.				
48r	g01200	In	4	Protector noster aspice deus et
	g01200a	InV	4	Quam dilecta tabernacula tua domine
	g01207	Gr	5	Bonum est confiteri domino et
	g01207a	GrV	5	Ad annuntiandum mane misericordiam tuam
48v	507036	Al	7	Alleluia Quoniam deus magnus dominus
	g01204	Of	8	Immittet angelus domini in circuitu
49r	g01211	Cm	1	Panis quem ego dedero caro
Dom. 16 p. Pent.				
	g01206	In	1	Inclina domine aurem tuam ad
	g01206c	InV	1	Laetifica animam servi tui quoniam
49v	g01201	Gr	5	Bonum est confidere domino et
	507043	Al	1	Alleluia Timebunt gentes nomen tuum
50r	g01210	Of	5	Exspectans exspectavi dominum et respexit
	g01177	Cm	6	Qui manducat carnem meam et
Dom. 17 p. Pent.				
50v	g01212	In	8	Miserere mihi domine quoniam ad
	g01212a	InV	8	Inclina domine aurem tuam et
	g00626	Gr	5	Timebunt gentes nomen tuum domine
	g00626b	GrV	5	Quoniam aedificavit dominus Sion et
51r	g01234	Al	2	Alleluia Confitemini domino et invocate
	g02305	Of	2	Domine in auxilium meum respice
51v	g01215	Cm	8	Domine memorabor justitiae tuae solius
Dom. 18 p. Pent.				
	g01216	In	1	Justus es domine et rectum
	g01217	Gr	1	Beata gens cujus est dominus
52r	g01217a	GrV	1	Verbo domini caeli firmati sunt
	g01238.2	Al	1	Alleluia Paratum cor meum deus
52v	g01220	Of	4	Oravi deum meum ego Daniel
	g01221	Cm	2	Vovete et reddite domino deo
53r	Dom. 19 p. Pent.			
	g01229	In	1	Da pacem domine sustinentibus te
	g01229c	InV	1	Laetatus sum in his quae
		Gr		Laetatus sum*
	507044	Al	1	Alleluia Qui timent dominum sperent

53v	g01231	Of	6	Sanctificavit Moyses altare domino offerrens
54r	g01232	Cm	4T	Tollite hostias et introite in
Dom. 20 p. Pent.	g01233	In	4	Salus populi ego sum dicit
	g01233a	InV	4	Attendite popule meus legem meam
	g00713	Gr	7	Dirigatur oratio mea sicut incensum
54v	g00713a	GrV	7	Elevatio manuum mearum sacrificium
	g01064	Al	1	Alleluia Dextera domini fecit virtutem
	g01235	Of	8	Si ambulavero in medio tribulationis
55r	g01236	Cm	7	Tu mandasti mandata tua custodiri
Dom. 21 p. Pent.	g01237	In	3	Omnia quae fecisti nobis domine
55v	g01241b	InV	3	Beati immaculati in via qui
	g01127	Gr		Oculi omnium*
	g02201	Al	1	Alleluia Qui confidunt in domino
56r	g01239	Of	1	Super flumina Babylonis illic sedimus
	g01240	Cm	4	Memento verbi tui servo tuo
Dom. 22 p. Pent.	g01241	In	4	In voluntate tua domine universa
56v	g01241b	InV	4	Beati immaculati in via qui
	g01242	Gr	2T	Domine refugium factus es nobis
	g01242a	GrV	2T	Priusquam montes fierent aut formaretur
57r	g01256	Al	7	Alleluia De profundis clamavi ad
	g01245	Of	2	Vir erat in terra nominee
57v	g01246	Cm	1	In salutari tuo anima mea
Dom. 23 p. Pent.	g01247	In	3	Si iniquitates observaveris domine domine
58r	g01247a	InV	3	De profundis clamavi ad te
	g00114	Gr		Ecce quam bonum*
	g02144	Al	3	Alleluia Qui sanat contritos corde
	g01251	Of	1	Recordare mei domine omni potentatui
58v	g01150	Cm	5	Dico vobis gaudium est angelis
Dom. 24 p. Pent.	g01253	In	6T	Dicit dominus ego cogito cogitationes
	g01253b	InV	6T	Benedixisti domine terram tuam avertisti
59r	g01254	Gr	7	Liberasti nos domine ex affligentibus
	g01254a	GrV	7	In deo laudabimur tota die
	g01535	Al	1	Alleluia Qui posuit fines tuos

59v				
	g01257	Of	2	De profundis clamavi ad te
	g01258	Cm	1	Amen dico vobis quidquid orantes
In Dedicatione Eccl.				
	g01401	In	2	Terribilis est locus iste hic
60r				
	g01401c	InV	2	Quam dilecta tabernacula tua domine virtutum
	g01402	Gr	5	Locus iste a deo factus
	g01402a	GrV	5	Deus cui adstat angelorum chorus
60v				
	g01404	Al	7	Alleluia Adorabo ad templum sanctum
Tempore res.				
	507009	Al		Alleluia Christus resurgens*
Tempore ascensionis				
	g02834	Al		Alleluia ascendens Christus*
Si in septuagesima evenerit				
	g03171	Tc	2	Domus mea domus orationis vocabitur
	g03171a	TcV	2	In ea omnis qui petit
61r				
	g03171b	TcV	2	Haec est domus domini firmiter
	g01406	Of	6	Domine deus in simplicitate cordis
	g01407	Cm	5	Domus mea domus orationis vocabitur
61v				
Vigilia Andreae				
	g00001	In	1	Dominus secus mare Galilaeae vidit
	g00001d	InV	1	At illi continuo relictis retibus
	g00002	Gr		Nimis honorati*
Si dominica fuit				
	g02563	Al		Alleluia Per manus autem*
	g01260	Of		Gloria et honore *
	g00004	Cm	4	Dicit Andreas Simoni fratri suo
62r				
Andreae				
	g00005	In		Mihi autem nimis*
	g00006	Gr		Constitues eos principes*
	g00008	Al	1	Alleluia Dilexit Andream dominus in
	g00009	Of		Mihi autem nimis*
	g00010	Cm	8	Venite post me faciam vos
Nicolai				
	g01271	In		Statuit ei dominus*
	g01332	Gr		Ecce sacerdos magnus*
	g01346	Al		Alleluia Justus germinabit*
	g01347	Of		Justus ut palma*
	g01354	Cm		Beatus servus*
In die conceptionis b. Marie virg.				
	501004.2	In		Gaudeamus omnes*
Cum ceteris ut in nativitate				
Luciae				
	g01380	In		Dilexisti justitiam*
	g01366	Gr		Dilexisti justitiam*
	g02713	Al		Alleluia Aemulor*

	g00083	Of		Offerentur regi virgines*
	g00302	Cm		Diffusa est gratia*
Annae				
	501004.3	In		Gaudeamus omnes*
	g01374	Gr		Adjuvabit eam deus*
62v				
		Al	7	Alleluia Anna mater eximia felix abrahe filia
	g01388	Of		Filiae regum in honore*
	g01400	Cm		Diffusa est gratia*
Thomae Apost.				
	g00005	In		Mihi autem nimis*
	g00444	Gr		In omnem terram*
	g00473	Al		Alleluia Nimis honorati*
	g00261	Of		Constitues eos principes*
	g01052	Cm	6T	Mitte manum tuam et cognosce
63r				
Stephani				
	g00559	In	1	Etenim sederunt principes et adversum
	g00559b	InV	1	Beati immaculati in via qui
	g00560	Gr	5	Sederunt principes et adversum me
63v				
	00560a	GrV	5	Adjuva me domine deus meus
	g00562	Al	2	Alleluia Video caelos apertos et
	g01357	Of		In virtute tua*
64r				
	g00564	Cm	8	Video caelos apertos et Jesum
Joannis Evang.				
	g01342	In	6	In medio ecclesiae aperuit os
64v				
	g01342a	InV	6	Jucunditatem et exultationem thesaurizavit super
	g00565	Gr	5	Exiit sermo inter fratres quod
	g00565a	GrV	5	Sed sic eum volo manere
	g00567	Al	2	Alleluia Hic est discipulus ille
65r				
	g01347	Of		Justus ut palma*
	g00568	Cm	2	Exiit sermo inter fratres quod
Nat. Innocentium				
	g00569	In	2	Ex ore infantium deus et
65v				
	g00569a.1	InV	2	Domine dominus noster quam admirabile
	g00570	Gr		Anima nostra*
Loco alleluia dicatur				
	–	Gr	2	Laus tua Deus
	–	GrV	2	Herodes iratus
	g03205	Al	2	Alleluia Hi sunt qui cum mulieribus
66r				
	g00576	Of		Anima nostra*
	g00577	Cm	7	Vox in Rama uditā est
Thomae episcopi et mart.				
	g01294	In		Laetabitur*
	g02233	Gr		Posuisti*

	g02236	Al	Alleluia Laetabitur*
	g01260	Of	Gloria et honore*
	g01293	Cm	Qui vult*
Silvestri			
	g01338	In	Sacerdotes tui*
	g01332	Gr	Ecce sacerdos*
	g00226	Al	Alleluia Inveni*
	g01288	Of	Inveni*
	g01354	Cm	Beatus servus*
Kanuti regis et mart.			
	g01290	In	In virtute tua*
	g01291	Gr	Beatus vir*
	g01302	Al	Alleluia Posuisti domine*
	g01260	Of	Gloria et honore*
	g01261	Cm	Magna est*
Felicis Nolani			
	g01349	In	Os justi*
	g02035	Gr	Juravit*
	g02070	Al	Alleluia disposui*
	g01260	Of	Gloria et honore*
	g01289	Cm	Posuisti*
Mauri			
	g01349	In	Os justi*
	g01360	Gr	Domine praevenisti*
	g02657	Al	Alleluia Os justi*
	g01363	Of	Desiderium*
	g01358	Cm	Amen dico vobis quod vos*
Marcelli, Pont.			
	g01271	In	Statuit*
	g01272	Gr	Inveni*
	g02148	Al	Alleluia Posui*
	g01278	Of	Veritas*
	g00012	Cm	Domine quinque*
Antonii			
66v			
	g01349	In	Os justi*
	g01343	Gr	Os justi*
	g02070	Al	Alleluia disposui*
	g01363	Of	Desiderium*
	g01354	Cm	Beatus servus*
Priscae			
	g00363	In	Loquebar*
	g01381	Gr	Specie tua*
	g02265	Al	Alleluia Veni electa*
	g01388	Of	Filiae regum*
	g01379	Cm	Feci iudicium*
Fabiani, Sebastiani			
	g01310	In	Intret*
	g01311	Gr	Gloriosus*
	g00041	Al	Alleluia Sancti tui*

Si in lxx (Septuagesima) evenerit

g01314	Tc	8	Qui seminant in lacrimis in
g01314a	TcV	8	Euntes ibant et flebant mittente
g01314b	TcV	8	Venientes autem venient cum exultatione
g00116	Of		Laetamini*

67r

g00043	Cm	2	Multitudo languentium et qui vexabantur
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Henrici

501004.?	In	1	Gaudeamus omnes in domino diem
	InV	1	Annunciabunt coeli justiciam eius
g01291	Gr		Beatus vir*
	Al	5	Alleluia Piae pater et patrone
g01288	Of		Inveni David*
g01299	Cm		Qui mihi*

Agnetis

g01373	In	2	Me exspectaverunt peccatores ut perderent
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68r

g01373a	InV	2	Beati immaculati in via qui
g01381	Gr		Specie tua*
g01383	Al		Alleluia Adducentur*

Si in lxx (Septuagesima) evenerit

g01314	Tc		Qui seminant*
g02069	Of		Offerentur*
g01389	Cm		Quinque*

Vincentii

g01294	In		Laetabitur*
g02233	Gr		Posuisti*
g02236	Al		Alleluia Laetabitur*

Si in lxx (Septuagesima) evenerit

g01285	Tc	8	Beatus vir qui timet dominum
g01285a	TcV	8	Potens in terra erit semen

68v

g01285b	TcV	8	Gloria et divitiae in domo
g01260	Of		Gloria et honore*
g01293	Cm		Qui vult*

Conversio Pauli

g02037	In	7	Laetemur omnes in domino hodiernum
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69r

g00045a	InV	7	Domine probasti me et cognovisti
g00046	Gr	5	Qui operatus est Petro in

69v

g0046a	GrV	5	Gratia dei in me vacua
g00048.1	Al	1	Alleluia Magnus sanctus Paulus

70r

Si in lxx (Septuagesima) evenerit

g00049	Tc	2	Tu es vas electionis sancta
g00050	TcV	2	Praedicator veritatis et doctor gentium
g00049a	TcV	2	Per te omnes gentes cognoverunt
g00052	TcV	2	Intercede pro nobis ad Deum

70v

g00009	Of		Mihi autem*
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	g01358	Cm		Amen dico vobis*
[Octava] Agnetis				
	g01390	In		Vultum tuum*
	g01366	Gr		Dilexisti*
	g01399	Al		Alleluia Specie*
	g02069	Of		Offerrentur*
	g01883	Cm		Simile est*
Ignatii				
	g01294	In		Laetabitur*
	g02233	Gr		Posuisti*
	g02236	Al		Alleluia Laetabitur*
	g01260	Of		Gloria et honore*
	g01293	Cm		Qui vult*
Purificatio Mariae				
	g01167	In		Suscepimus*
	g00073	Gr	5	Suscepimus deus misericordiam tuam in
	g00073a	GrV	5	Sicut audivimus ita et vidimus
71r				
	g01404	Al		Alleluia Adorabo ad templum* ²¹
Si in lxx (Septuagesima) evenerit				
	g01413	Tc	2	Gaude Maria virgo cunctas haereses
	g01413a	TcV	2	Quae Gabrielis archangeli dictis credidisti
	g01413b	TcV	2	Dum virgo deum et hominem
71v				
	g01413c	TcV	2	Dei genetrix intercede pro nobis
	g01421	Of	1	Felix namque es sacra virgo
	g00080	Cm	8	Responsum accepit Simeon a spiritu
72r				
Blasii				
	g01294	In		Laetabitur justus*
	g02233	Gr		Posuisti*
	g02236	Al		Alleluia Laetabitur*
	g01260	Of		Gloria et honore*
	g01293	Cm		Qui vult*
Agathae				
	501004.1	In		Gaudeamus omnes*
	501004a	InV		Eructavit cor meum*
	g01374	Gr		Adjuvabit*
	g00023	Al		Alleluia Diffusa*
Vel tractus				
	g01314	Tc		Qui seminant*
	g01388	Of		Filiae regum*
	g00084	Cm	6	Qui me dignatus est ab
Simeonis				
	g01229	In	1	Da pacem domine sustinentibus te
72v				
	g00327a	InV	1	Beatus vir qui timet dominum

²¹ The incipit is supplied with a marginal addition “In die dedicationis eccle[sie] Alleluia Ador[abo].” The addition indicates that the notated alleluia can be found in the feast of *Dedicatio ecclesiae* (folios 59v–60v).

	g01332	Gr		Ecce propheta ²² magnus*
	g00075	Al		Alleluia Inveni*
vel	g01285	Tc		Beatus vir*
	g01278	Of		Veritas mea*
	g00080	Cm		Responsum*
Valentini	g01290	In		In virtute*
	g01291	Gr		Beatus vir*
	g01302	Al		Alleluia Posuisti*
	g01357	Of		In virtute tua*
	g01261	Cm		Magna est*
Sigfridi	g01271	In		Statuit*
	g01332	Gr		Ecce sacerdos*
	g04540	Al	2	Alleluia O decus presulum sancte Sigfride familiam
73r	g01285	Tc		Beatus vir*
	g01278	Of		Veritas mea*
	g00318	Cm		Fidelis servus*
Cathedra Petri	g01271	In		Statuit*
	g00027	Gr	2T	Exaltent eum in ecclesia plebis
	g00027a	GrV	2T	Confiteantur domino misericordiae ejus et
73v	g00030	Tc	2	Tu es Petrus et super
	g00030a	TcV	2	Et portae inferi non praevallebunt
	g00030b.1	TcV	2	Et quodcumque ligaveris super terram
74r	g00030c	TcV	2	Et quodcumque solveris super terram
	g01278	Of		Veritas mea*
	g00262	Cm	2	Tu es Petrus et super
Matthiaei	g00005	In		Mihi autem nimis*
	g00002	Gr		Nimis honorati*
	g01275	Tc	8	Desiderium animae ejus tribuisti ei
74v	g01275a	TcV	8	Quoniam praevenisti eum in benedictionibus
	g01275b	TcV	8	Posuisti super caput ejus coronam
		Of		In omnem terram*
		Cm		Vos qui secuti*
Thomae de Aquino Confessoris et Ecclesiae Doctoris ²³	g01342	In		In medio ecclesiae*
	g01343	Gr		Os justi*
	g01285	Tc		Beatus vir*
	g01278	Of		Veritas mea*

²² Missale Aboense, 503ab: Ecce sacerdos magnus

²³ The rubric in the manuscript is unclear. Apparently, efforts have been made to correct the initially incorrect rubric, modifying it from “Gregorii” to “Thom”. The combination of chants and the location of the feast confirm that the celebrated saint is Thomae de Aquino Confessoris et Ecclesiae Doctoris.

75r

g00012 Cm Domine quinque*
Gregorii [Sancti gregorij officium]
g01280 In Sacerdotes dei*
g02035 Gr Juravit dominus*
g01285 Tc Beatus vir*
g01278 Of Veritas mea*
g00318 Cm Fidelis servus*

Benedicti

g01349 In Os justi*
g01360 Gr Domine praevenisti*
g01285 Tc Beatus vir*
g01363 Of Desiderium animae*
g01358 Cm Amen dico vobis*

Annuntiatio Mariae

501007 In Rorate caeli*
g02220 Gr Tollite portas*
g00119 Tc 2 Ave Maria gratia plena dominus
g00119a TcV 2 Benedicta tu in mulieribus et
g00119d TcV 2 Spiritus sanctus superveniet in te

75v

g00119e TcV 2 Ideoque et quod nascetur ex
507002 Al Alleluia Virga Jesse floruit*
507004.1 Al Alleluia Surrexit dominus et occurrens*
g00533 Of Ave Maria gratia*
503007 Cm Ecce virgo*

Ambrosii

g01271 In Statuit*
g01332 Gr Ecce sacerdos*
g01285 Tc Beatus vir qui timet*

Temp. Res.

g00226 Al Alleluia Inveni*
008415 Al Alleluia Angelus domini*
g01278 Of Veritas mea*
g00318 Cm Fidelis servus*

Tiburtii, Valeriani, Maximi

g01305 In 3 Sancti tui domine benedicent te
g01305a InV 3 Exaltabo te deus meus rex

76r

g00024 Al 4 Alleluia Gaudete justi in domino
g00116 Of Laetamini in domino*
g01309 Cm Gaudete justi*

Compassio Mariae TP

g01390 In Vultum tuum*
Al 3 Alleluia Dolorum matris virginis

76v

Al 5 Alleluia Trenae Mariae Virginis sub cruce quas sustinuit

vel

77r

g01409 Gr Benedicta et venerabilis*

	502003.1	Of		Recordare virgo mater*
	g01419	Cm		Beata viscera*
Georgii				
	g01300	In	7	Protexisti me deus a convent
	g01300a	InV	7	Exaudi deus orationem meam cum
	g01362	Al		Alleluia Justus ut palma*
	008415	Al		Alleluia Angelus domini*
	g01303	Of	7	Confitebuntur caeli mirabilia tua domine
77v				
	g01304	Cm	5	Laetabitur justus in domino et
Marci				
	g01300	In		Protexisti me deus*
	g02343	Al		Alleluia Primus ad Sion*
	008426	Al		Alleluia In die resurrectionis meae*
	g02066	Of	1	Repleti sumus mane misericordia tua
78r				
	g02065	Cm	8	Ego sum vitis vera et
Vitalis, Valeriae				
	g01300	In		Protexisti me*
	g00323	Al		Alleluia Justus non conturbabitur*
	g02066	Of		Repleti sumus mane*
	g02065	Cm		Ego sum vitis*
Petri, Mart.				
	g01300	In		Protexisti me*
	g03230	Al	5	Alleluia Felix ex fructu triplici
78v				
	g02080	Al		Alleluia Surrexit pastor*
	g01298	Of		Posuisti domine*
	g02065	Cm		Ego sum vitis*
Philippi, Jacobi				
	g00185	In	1	Exclamaverunt ad te domine in
	g00185a	InV	1	Exsultate justi in domino rectos
79r				
	g02359	Al	2	Alleluia Stabant justi in magna
	008426	Al		Alleluia In die resurrectionis meae*
	g02834	Al		Alleluia Ascendens*
	g01303	Of		Confitebuntur*
	g00187	Cm	4	Tanto tempore vobiscum sum et
79v				
Inventio Crucis				
	g00180	In		Nos autem*
	g00182	Al	8	Alleluia Dulce lignum dulces clavos
	g01023	Al		Alleluia Surrexit dominus de sepulcro*
	g02834	Al		Alleluia Ascendens*
	g00376	Of	2	Protege domine plebem tuam per
80r				
	g02068	Cm	8	Per lignum servi facti sumus
Corone domini				
	501004.15	In	1	Gaudeamus omnes in domino diem festum ... corone
	501004g	InV	1	Omnes gentes plaudite manibus jubilate
	g03231	Al	1	Alleluia Diadema spineum veneremur hodie

81r

g01023	Al	Alleluia Surrexit dominus de sepulcro*
g02834	Al	Alleluia Ascendens*
g01260	Of	Gloria et honore*
g01289	Cm	Posuisti domine*

Joannis Port. Lat.

g01342	In	In medio ecclesiae*
g00567	Al	Alleluia Hic est discipulus*
008426	Al	Alleluia In die resurrectionis*
g01080	Al	Alleluia Ascendens*
g02066	Of	Repleti sumus mane*
g02065	Cm	Ego sum vitis*

Gordiani, Epimachi

g01305	In	Sancti tui domine*
g02244	Al	Alleluia Sancti et justi*
g01317	Of	Mirabilis deus*
g00209	Cm	Justorum animae*

Pancratii et Soc. [Nerei Achillei et pancracij marto ff]

g00188	In	3	Ecce oculi domini super timentes
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81v

g00188a	InV	3	Exsultate justi in domino rectos
g00024	Al		Alleluia Gaudete justi*
g01303	Of		Confitebuntur caeli*
g01309	Cm		Gaudete justi*

In translacione beati Dominici officium Sicut in alio festo tempore resurrectione. et in

008426	Al		Alleluia In die resurrectionis*
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tempore ascensionis et in

g01080	Al		Alleluia Ascendens*
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Urbani

g01338	In		Sacerdotes*
[g01272	Gr		Inveni David* ?]
g01302	Al		Alleluia Posuisti*
g01278	Of		Veritas mea*
g00318	Cm		Fidelis servus*

Marcellini, Petri

g00113	In	2	Clamaverunt justi et dominus exaudivit
g00113a	InV	2	Benedicam dominum in omni tempore

82r

g01311	Gr		Gloriosus deus*
g00325	Al		Alleluia Fulgebunt*
g01317	Of		Mirabilis deus*
g00209	Cm		Justorum animae*

Erasmi ep. [In festo sancti Erasmi officium]²⁴

Primi, Feliciani

g01319	In		Sapientiam sanctorum*
g00475	Gr		Exultabunt*
g00040	Al		Alleluia Mirabilis*
g00116	Of		Laetamini in domino*

²⁴ The feast is referenced in the manuscript. However, the space allocated for the chant combination has been left empty.

	g00225	Cm	Ego vos elegi*
Barnabae			
	g00005	In	Mihi autem*
	g00444	Gr	In omnem*
	g00473.1	Al	Alleluia Nimis honorati*
	g01080	Al	Alleluia Ascendens*
	g00025	Of	In omnem*
	g00359	Cm	Vos qui*
Eskilli			
	501004	In	Gaudeamus omnes*
	g02233	Gr	Posuisti domine*
	g04535	Al	Alleluia Grex susperiat*
	g01260	Of	Gloria et honore*
	g01289	Cm	Posuisti domine*
Basilidis et Soc.			
	g01310	In	Intret in conspectu*
	g00470	Gr	Vindica domine*
	g01328	Al	Alleluia Te Martyrum*
	g01323	Of	Exultabunt*
	g00472	Cm	Posuerunt mortalia*
Marci, Marcellini			
	g01325	In	Salus autem*
	g00570	Gr	Anima nostra*
	g02244	Al	Alleluia Sancti et justi*
	g01323	Of	Exultabunt*
	g00695	Cm	Amen dico vobis quod uni*
Translatio Henrici [In festo sancti Henrici]			
	501004	In	Gaudeamus omnes
	g01291	Gr	Beatus vir*
	g04536	Al	Alleluia Pie presul
	g01288	Of	Inveni David*
	g01299	Cm	Qui mihi ministrat me sequatur*
Erici			
	501004	In	Gaudeamus omnes*
	g01156	Al	Alleluia Domine in virtute*
	g04539	Al	Alleluia Rex piae*
	g01298	Of	Posuisti domine*
	g01261	Cm	Magna est*
Gervasii, Protasii			
	g00228	In	3 Loquetur dominus pacem in plebem
	g00228a	InV	3 Benedixisti domine terram tuam avertisti
82v			
	g00038	Gr	Justorum animae*
	g01322	Al	Alleluia Justi epulentur*
	g00576	Of	Anima nostra*
	g00472	Cm	Posuerunt mortalia*
Joannis Baptistae			
	g00239	In	De ventre matris meae vocavi
	g00239a	InV	2 Audite insulae et attendite populi
83r			
	g00240	Gr	5 Priusquam te formarem in utero

	g00240a	GrV	5	Misit dominus manum suam et
	g02228	Al	1	Alleluia Inter natos mulierum non
83v				
	g01347	Of		Justus ut palma*
	g00243	Cm	2	Tu puer propheta altissimi vocaberis
Joannis, Pauli				
	g00227	In	2	Multae tribulationes justorum et de
84r				
	g00227a	InV	2	Benedicam dominum in omni tempore
	g00114	Gr		Ecce quam bonum et quam*
	g02330	Al	1	Alleluia Isti sunt duae olivae
84v				
	g00244	Of		Gloriabuntur*
	g01318	Cm	1	Et si coram hominibus tormenta
85r				
Vigilia Petri, Pauli				
	g00255	In	4	Dicit dominus Petro cum esses
	g00255a	InV	4	Caeli enarrant gloriam dei et
85v				
	g00444	Gr		In omnem*
	g00473	Al		Alleluia Nimis*
	g00009	Of		Mihi autem*
	g00256	Cm	6T	Simon Joannis diligis me plus
Petri, Pauli				
	g00257	In	3	Nunc scio vere quia misit
86r				
	g00257a	InV	3	Domine probasti me et cognovisti me
	g00006	Gr		Constitues*
	g02235.1	Al	1	Alleluia Beatus es Simon Bar
86v				
	g00261	Of		Constitues*
	g00262	Cm		Tu es Petrus*
Pauli				
	g00045	In	1	Scio cui credidi et certus
	g00045c.1	InV	1	De reliquo reposita est mihi
	g00046	Gr		Qui operatus est*
	g00048	Al		Alleluia Magnus sanctus*
	g00005	Of		Mihi autem*
	g01358	Cm		Amen dico vobis quod vos*
Octava Joannis Bapt.				
	g01319	In		Sapientiam sanctorum*
	g00444	Gr		In omnem*
	g02563	Al		Alleluia Per manus autem*
	g01323	Of		Exultabunt*
	g00225	Cm		Ego vos elegi*
Octava Apostolorum				
	g01319	In		Sapientiam sanctorum*
	g00444	Gr		In omnem*
	g02330	Al		Alleluia Isti sunt duae*
	g01323	Of		Exultabunt sancti*
	g00225	Cm		Ego vos elegi*

Septem Fratrum

87r

g00290	In	1	Laudate pueri dominum laudate nomen
g00290b	InV	1	Sit nomen domini benedictum ex
g00114	Gr		Ecce quam bonum*
g02078	Al	4	Alleluia Laudate pueri dominum laudate
g00576	Of		Anima nostra*
g00117	Cm	1	Quicumque fecerit voluntatem patris mei

87v

Margaritae

g00363	In		Loquebar*
g01381	Gr		Specie tua*
g02713	Al		Alleluia Aemulor*
g00083	Of		Offerentur*
g01883	Cm		Simile est regnum*

Divisio Apostolorum

g00005	In		Mihi autem*
g00444	Gr		In omnem terram*
g02563	Al		Alleluia Per manus autem*
g00025	Of		In omnem*
g00225	Cm		Vos qui secuti*

Alexii

g01349	In		Os justi*
g01343	Gr		Os justi*
g01346	Al		Alleluia Justus germinabit*
g01363	Of		Desiderium*
g01358	Cm		Amen dico vobis quod vos*

Praxedis

g01380	In		Dilexisti justitiam*
g01366	Gr		Dilexisti justitiam*
g00023	Al		Alleluia Diffusa*
g01378	Of		Diffusa est*
g01389	Cm		Quinque prudentes*

Mariae Magdalenae

501004.11	In		Gaudeamus omnes*
g00412	Gr		Propter veritatem*
507004.1	Al		Alleluia Surrexit dominus et occurrens*
g01018	Of		Angelus domini*
g00302	Cm		Diffusa est*

Apollinaris

g01280	In		Sacerdotes dei benedicite*
g02344	Gr		Justus non conturbabitur*
g01302	Al		Alleluia Posuisti domine*
g01278	Of		Veritas mea*
g01279	Cm		Semel juravi*

Jacobi

g00005	In		Mihi autem*
g00006	Gr		Constitues*
g02067	Al		Alleluia Non vos me*
g00009	Of		Mihi autem*
g00359	Cm		Vos qui secuti*

Marthae		
501004.12	In	Gaudeamus omnes*
g00412	Gr	Propter veritatem*
g02265	Al	Alleluia Veni electa*
g01388	Of	Filiae regum*
g00302	Cm	Diffusa est*
Nazarii, Celsi		
g00037	In	Justi epulentur et*
g00470	Gr	Vindica*
g02330	Al	Alleluia Isti sunt duae*
g00576	Of	Anima nostra*
g01324	Cm	Dico autem*
Olavi		
g01294	In	Laetabitur justus*
g02233	Gr	Posuisti domine*
g01156	Al	Alleluia Domine in virtute*
g01260	Of	Gloria et honore*
g01261	Cm	Magna est*
Felicis		
g02264	In	Sacerdotes ejus*
g01339	Gr	Sacerdotes ejus*
g02070	Al	Alleluia disposui*
g00116	Of	Laetamini*
g00209	Cm	Justorum*
Abdonis, Sennis		
g01310	In	Intret in conspectu*
g01311	Gr	Gloriosus deus*
g01328	Al	Alleluia Te martyrurum*
g01317	Of	Mirabilis deus*
g00472	Cm	Posuerunt*
De patronis		
g01325	In	Salus autem*
g01311	Gr	Gloriosus deus*
g01322	Al	Alleluia Justi epulentur*
g01323	Of	Exultabunt*
g01309	Cm	Gaudete*
Helenae Schedviensis		
501004	In	Gaudeamus omnes*
g00412	Gr	Propter veritatem*
g04526	Al	6T Alleluia Helena vesgocie decus
88r		
g01378	Of	Diffusa est*
g01379	Cm	Feci iudicium*
Germani		
g01271	In	Statuit*
g01272	Gr	Inveni David*
g02148	Al	Alleluia Posui*
g01278	Of	Veritas mea*
g01279	Cm	Semel*
Vincula Petri		
g00257	In	Nunc scio vere*

	g00006	Gr		Constitues*
	g00306	Al	1	Alleluia Solve jubente Deo terrarum
88v	g00261	Of		Constitues*
	g00262	Cm		Tu es Petrus*
Stephani, Pont.				
	g02264	In		Sacerdotes ejus*
	g01343	Gr		Os justi meditabitur*
	g01345	Al		Alleluia Amavit*
	g01288	Of		Inveni David*
	g00012	Cm		Domine quinque*
Inventio Stephani				
Officium, responsorium, ²⁵ alleluia, offertorium, communio sicut in alio festa [66r-v].				
Dominici				
	g01342	In		In medio ecclesiae*
	g01343	Gr		Os justi*
	g02753.1	Al		Alleluia Pie pater Dominice tuorum
	g01363	Of		Desiderium*
	g00318	Cm		Fidelis servus*
Vigilia Laurentii				
	g00327	In	3	Dispersit dedit pauperibus justitia ejus
89r	g00327a	InV	3	Beatus vir qui timet dominum
	g00328	Gr	2T	Dispersit dedit pauperibus justitia ejus
	g00328a	GrV	2T	Potens in terra erit semen
89v	Si dominica fuit			
	g02827	Al		Alleluia Beatus vir*
	g00330	Of	7	Oratio mea munda est et
	g01293	Cm		Qui vult*
Laurentii				
	g00331	In		Confessio et pulchritudo*
	g00332	Gr	5	Probasti domine cor meum et
90r	g00332a	GrV	5	Igne me examinasti et non
	g00334.1	Al	7	Alleluia Levita Laurentius bonum opus
90v	g00335	Of	4	Confessio et pulchritudo in conspectu
	g01299	Cm	5	Qui mihi ministrat me sequitur
Hippolytus, Martyr				
	g00037	In		Justi epulentur*
	g00038	Gr		Justorum animae*
	g00041	Al		Alleluia Sancti tui*
	g00576	Of		Anima nostra*
	g01324	Cm		Dico autem*
Vig. Assump. Mariae				
	g01408	In		Salve sancta parens*
	g01409	Gr		Benedicta et venerabilis*

²⁵ Here the term responsorium is used instead of graduale.

	507002	Al		Alleluia Virga Jesse floruit*
	g00277	Of	8	Beata es Virgo Maria quae
91r				
	g01419	Cm		Beata viscera Mariae*
Assumptio Mariae				
	501004.2	In	1	Gaudeamus omnes in domino diem
	501004a	InV	1	Eructavit cor meum verbum bonum
91v				
		Gr		Propter veritatem*
	g02249	Al	8	Alleluia Hodie Maria virgo caelos
	g01421	Of		Felix namque es*
	g01419	Cm		Beata viscera Mariae*
Octava Laurentii				
	g02209	In	8	Probasti domine cor meum et
92r				
	g02209a	InV	8	Exaudi domine justitiam meam intende
Cetera sicut in festo ipsius				
Bernardi				
	g01349	In		Os justi meditabitur*
	g01360	Gr		Domine praevenisti*
	g02657	Al		Alleluia Os justi*
	g01363	Of		Desiderium animae*
	g01358	Cm		Amen dico vobis quod vos*
Bartholomaei				
	g00063	In		Mihi autem*
	g00444	Gr		In omnem*
	g00473	Al		Alleluia Nimis*
	ah54087	Of		Constitues*
	g00261	Cm		Vos qui secuti*
Ludovici				
	g01349	In		Os justi meditabitur*
	g01360	Gr		Domine praevenisti*
	g01346	Al		Alleluia Justi epulentur*
	g01363	Of		Desiderium animae*
	g00318	Cm		Fidelis servus*
Augustini				
	g01342	In		In medio ecclesiae*
	g01343	Gr		Os justi meditabitur*
	g01346	Al		Alleluia Justus germinabit*
	g01278	Of		Veritas mea*
	g00318	Cm		Fidelis servus*
Decoll. Jo. Bapt.				
	g01355	In	1	Justus ut palma florebit sicut
92v				
	g01355a	InV	1	Bonum est confiteri domino et
	g02233	Gr		Posuisti domine*
	g02547	Al	1	Alleluia Misso Herodes spiculatore praecepit
	g01363	Of		Desiderium animae*
	g01261	Cm		Magna est*
Nativitas Mariae				
	501004.2	In	1	Gaudeamus omnes in domino diem

93r	501004a	InV	1	Eructavit cor meum verbum bonum
	g00412	Gr		Propter veritatem*
	g02216	Al	7	Alleluia Nativitas gloriosae virginis Mariae
	g01421	Of		Felix namque es*
	g01419	Cm		Beata viscera*
Exaltatio Crucis				
	g00180	In		Nos autem*
	505005	Gr		Christus factus est*
	g00182	Al		Alleluia Dulce*
	g00376	Of		Protege domine*
93v	g00184	Cm	4T	Per signum Crucis de inimicis
Euphemiae				
	g01390	In		Vultum tuum deprecabuntur*
	g01381	Gr		Specie tua*
	g02906	Al		Alleluia Haec est virgo*
	g00083	Of		Offerrentur regi*
	g01393	Cm		Simile est regnum*
Vigilia Matthaei				
	g01259	In	3	Ego autem sicut oliva fructificavi
	g01259a	InV	3	Quid gloriaris in malitia qui
94r	g01350	Gr		Justus ut palma*
	008416.1	Al		Alleluia Beatus vir qui timet*
	g01260	Of		Gloria et honore*
	g01289	Cm		Posuisti domine*
Matthaei				
	g00005	In		Mihi autem nimis*
	g00002	Gr		Nimis honorati*
	g02149	Al		Alleluia In omnem terram*
	g00025	Of		In omnem terram*
	g00225	Cm		Ego vos*
Mauritii				
	g01325	In		Salus autem*
	g01311	Gr		Gloriosus deus*
	g02244	Al		Alleluia Sancti et justii*
	g01317	Of		Mirabilis deus*
	g00472	Cm		Posuerunt*
Michaelis				
	g02711	In	3	Benedicite dominum omnes angeli ejus
	g02711	InV	3	Benedic anima mea domino et omnia
	g02712	Gr		Benedicite dominum omnes angeli ejus
94v	g02712a	GrV	3	Benedic anima mea domino et
	g01429	Al	1	Alleluia In conspectu angelorum psallam
	g00397	Of	1	Stetit angelus juxta aram temple
95r	g00398	Co	3	Benedicite omnes angeli domini domino

Hieronimi		
g01349	In	Os justi*
g01343	Gr	Os justi meditabitur*
g01302	Al	Alleluia Posuisti* ²⁶
g01363	Of	Desiderium*
g00318	Cm	Fidelis*
Remigii		
g01271	In	Statuit*
g01332	Gr	Ecce sacerdos*
g01341	Al	Alleluia Juravit*
g01288	Of	Inveni David*
g01354	Cm	Beatus servus*
Francisci		
g01349	In	Os justi*
g01360	Gr	Domine praevenisti*
g01346	Al	Alleluia Justus germinabit*
g01363	Of	Desiderium*
g01358	Cm	Amen dico vobis quod vos*
Marci, Pont.		
g01280	In	Sacerdotes Dei*
g01272	Gr	Inveni David*
g02568	Al	Alleluia Iste sanctus*
95v		
g01278	Of	Veritas mea*
g01354	Cm	Beatus servus*
Dionysii		
g01310	In	Intret in conspectu*
g01311	Gr	Gloriosus deus*
g02217	Al	Alleluia Judicabunt sancti*
g00116	Of	Laetamini in domino*
g01309	Cm	Gaudete justi*
Lucae		
g01342	In	In medio*
g01343	Gr	Os justi meditabitur*
g02343	Al	Alleluia Primus*
g01298	Of	Posuisti domine*
g00012	Cm	Domine quinque*
XI milium Virginum		
g01390	In	Vultum tuum*
g01311	Gr	Gloriosus deus*
g01383	Al	Alleluia Adducentur*
g00083	Of	Offerrentur regi*
g01389	Cm	Quinque*
Vigilia Simonis, Judae		
g01310	In	Intret in conspectu*
g00470	Gr	Vindica domine*
g02563	Al	Alleluia Per manus autem*
g01323	Of	Exultabunt*

²⁶ The scribe may have mistaken the chant incipit. The more common Alleluia chant associated with Jerome is g02148 *Alleluia Posui adjutorium*, also found in the Missale Aboense.

	g00209	Cm		Justorum*
Simonis, Judae				
	g00005	In		Mihi autem nimis*
	g00002	Gr		Nimis honorati*
	g02067	Al		Alleluia Non vos me*
	g00025	Of		In omnem terram*
	g00359	Cm		Vos qui secuti*
Vig. Om. Sanctorum				
96r	g00324	In	3	Timete Dominum omnes sancti ejus
	g00324a	InV	3	Benedicam dominum in omni tempore
	g01311	Gr		Gloriosus deus*
	g00325	Al		Alleluia Fulgebunt justii*
	g00116	Of		Laetamini in domino*
	g00225	Cm		Ego vos elegi*
Omnium Sanctorum				
	501004.5	In	1	Gaudeamus omnes in domino diem ...collaudant
	501004e	InV	1	Exsultate justii in domino rectos
96v	g00478	Gr		Timete dominum*
	g02217	Al		Alleluia Judicabunt sancti*
	g01317	Of		Mirabilis deus*
	g01309	Cm		Gaudete justii*
Commemoratio animarum				
	g01566	In	4	Requiem aeternam dona eis domine
	g01566a	InV	4	Te decet hymnus deus in
	g01567	Gr	2T	Requiem aeternam dona eis domine
97r	g01567a	GrV	2T	Animae eorum in bonis demorentur
	g01569	Tc	8	Absolute domine animas omnium fidelium
97v	g01569a	TcV	8	Et gratia tua illis succurrente mereantur
	g01569b	TcV	8	Et lucis aeternae beatitudine perfrui
	g01573	Of	2	Domine Jesu Christe rex gloriae
	g01573a	OfV	2	Hostias et preces
	g01576	Cm	8	Lux aeterna luceat eis domine
98v	Pro defunctis ²⁷			
	g02389	In	4	Si enim credimus quod Jesus
	g02389a	InV	4	Et sicut in Adam omnes
	g00772	Gr	1	Si ambulem in medio umbrae
99r	g00772a	GrV	1	Virga tua et baculus tuus
	g02374	Tc		Sicut cervus*
Require in die parasceves				
		Of		Domine Jesu Christe*
	g02654	Cm	8T	Pro quorum memoria corpus
99v	Theodori Tiro			

²⁷ Item pro maiori defuncto officium

	g01290	In		In virtute tua*
	g01360	Gr		Domine praevenisti*
	g02568	Al		Alleluia Iste sanctus*
	g01260	Of		Gloria et honore*
	g01289	Cm		Posuisti domine*
Martini				
	g01271	In		Statuit ei dominus*
	g01272	Gr		Inveni David*
	g02218	Al		Alleluia Hic Martinus pauper et
	g01278	Of		Veritas mea*
	g00318	Cm		Fidelis servus*
Briccii				
	g01271	In		Statuit ei dominus*
	g01332	Gr		Ecce sacerdos*
	g01341	Al		Alleluia Juravit*
	g01288	Of		Inveni David*
	g01354	Cm		Beatus servus*
Elisabeth				
	g01380	In		Dilexisti*
	g00486	Gr		Audi filia et vide et*
	g02265	Al		Alleluia Veni*
	g01388	Of		Filiae regum*
	g01883	Cm		Simile est*
Edmundi				
	g01290	In		In virtute*
	g02233	Gr		Posuisti domine*
	g02236	Al		Alleluia Laetabitur*
	g01357	Of		In virtute tua*
	g01293	Cm		Qui vult*
Caeciliae				
	g00363	In		Loquebar de*
	g00486	Gr		Audi filia*
	g02265	Al		Alleluia Veni*
	g02069	Of		Offerrentur regi*
	g01372	Cm		Confundantur*
100r				
Clementis				
	g00488	In	1	Dicit dominus sermones mei quos
	g00488a	InV	1	Domine exaudi orationem meam et
	g02035	Gr		Juravit dominus*
	g01362	Al		Alleluia Justus ut palma*
	g01298	Of		Posuisti*
	g01354	Cm		Beatus servus*
Chrysogoni				
	g01290	In		In virtute*
	g01291	Gr		Beatus vir*
	g02568	Al		Alleluia Iste sanctus*
	g01260	Of		Gloria et honore*
	g01261	Cm		Magna est*
Catharinae				
	g00363	In		Loquebar de*

	g01381	Gr		Specie tua*
	g02265	Al		Alleluia Veni*
	g01388	Of		Filiae regum*
	g01379	Cm		Feci iudicium*
Lini				
	g02264	In		Sacerdotes ejus*
	g01343	Gr		Os iusti*
	g01345	Al		Alleluia Amavit*
	g01288	Of		Inveni David*
	g00012	Cm		Domine quinque*
100v				
In vigilia unius apostoli				
	g01259	In	3	Ego autem sicut oliva fructificavi
	g01259a	InV	3	Quid gloriaris in malitia qui
	g01350	Gr		Justus ut palma*
	008416.1	Al		Alleluia Beatus vir qui timet*
	g01260	Of		Gloria et honore*
	g01261	Cm		Magna est*
Unius vel plur. apostolorum off.				
	g00005	In	2	Mihi autem nimis honorati sunt
101r				
	g00005a	InV	2	Domine probasti me et cognovisti
	g00002	Gr	2T	Nimis honorati sunt amici tui
	g00002a	GrV	2T	Dinumerabo eos et super arenam
101v				
	g00006	Gr	5	Constitues eos principes super
	g00006a	GrV	5	Pro patribus tuis nati sunt
102r				
	g00444	Gr	2T	In omnem terram exivit sonus
	g00444a	GrV	2T	Caeli enarrant gloriam dei et
102v				
	g00473	Al	8	Alleluia Nimis honorati sunt amici
	g02067	Al	1	Alleluia Non vos me elegistis
103r				
	g02563	Al	4	Alleluia Per manus autem apostolorum
	g02149	Al	6	Alleluia In omnem terram exivit terram exivit
103v				
	g02343	Al	5	Alleluia Primus ad Sion dicet
	g00009	Of	3	Mihi autem nimis honorati sunt
104r				
	g00261	Of	3	Constitues eos principes super omnem
	g00025	Of	2	In omnem terram exivit sonus
104v				
	g01358	Cm	1	Amen dico vobis quod vos
	g00102	Cm	1	Vos qui secuti estis me
	g00225	Cm	1	Ego vos elegi de mundo
105r				
In festo unius Martyris [et Pont.]				
	g01294	In	8	Laetabitur justus in domino et
	g01294a	InV	8	Exaudi deus orationem meam cum

item				
	g01290	In	7	In virtute tua domine laetabitur
105v				
	g01290d	InV	7	Quoniam praevenisti eum in benedictionibus
item aliud				
	g01300	In	7	Protexisti me deus a convent
	g01300a	InV	7	Exaudi deus orationem meam [cum ...]
106r				
	g02233	Gr	1	Posuisti domine super caput ejus
	g02233a	GrV	1	Desiderium animae ejus tribuisti ei
	g01291	Gr5	5	Beatus vir qui timet dominum
107r				
	g01291a	GrV	5	Potens in terra erit semen
	g01350	Gr	2T	Justus ut palma florebit sicut
	g01207a	GrV	2T	Ad annuntiandum mane misericordiam tuam
107v				
	g02344	Gr	5	Justus non conturbabitur quia dominus
	g02344a	GrV	5	Tota die miseretur et commodat
108r				
	g02827	Al	5	Alleluia Beatus vir qui timet
	g01302	Al	1	Alleluia Posuisti domine super caput
	g01362	Al	1	Alleluia Justus ut palma florebit
108v				
	g02236	Al	7	Alleluia Laetabitur justus in domino
109r				
	g00323	Al	2	Alleluia Justus non conturbabitur quia
	g02568	Al	8	Alleluia Iste sanctus digne in
109v				
	g01260	Of	1	Gloria et honore coronasti eum
	g01347	Of	4	Justus ut palma florebit sicut
110r				
	g01357	Of	6T	In virtute tua domine laetabitur Justus
	g01298	Of	8	Posuisti domine in capite ejus
110v				
	g01261	Cm	4	Magna est gloria ejus in
	g01289	Cm	6	Posuisti domine in capite ejus
	g01293	Cm	1	Qui vult venire post me
In festo plurimorum martyrum				
	g01310	In	4	Intret in conspectu tuo domine
111r				
	g01310a	InV	4	Deus venerunt gentes in hereditatem
aliud				
	g01319	In	1	Sapientiam sanctorum narrant populi et
111v				
	g01319a	InV	1	Exsultate justi in domino rectos
aliud				
	g01325	In	1	Salus autem justorum a domino
	g01325a	InV	1	Noli aemulari in malignantibus neque
aliud				
	g00037	In	6	Justi epulentur et exsultent in
	g00037a	InV	6	Exsurgat deus et dissipentur inimici

112r				
item aliud				
	g01305	In	3	Sancti tui domine benedicent te
	g01305a	InV	3	Exaltabo te deus meus rex
	g00570	Gr	5	Anima nostra sicut passer erepta
112v				
	g00570a	GrV	5	Laqueus contritus est et nos
	g01311	Gr	2	Gloriosus deus in sanctis mirabilis
113r				
	g01311a	GrV	1	Dextera tua domine glorificata est
	g00038	Gr	5	Justorum animae in manu dei
113v				
	g00038a	GrV	5	Visi sunt oculis insipientium mori
	g00470	Gr	5	Vindica domine sanguinem sanctorum
	g00470a	GrV	5	Posuerunt mortalia servorum tuorum
114r				
	g00114	Gr	1	Ecce quam bonum et quam
	g00114a	GrV	1	Sicut unguentum in capite quod
114v				
	g00475	Gr	2T	Exultabunt sancti in gloria laetabuntur
	g00475a	GrV	2T	Cantate domino canticum novum
	g00478	Gr	1	Timete dominum omnes sancti
115r				
	g00478a	GrV	1	Inquirentes autem dominum
	g02244	Al	7	Alleluia Sancti et justi in
115v				
	g01328	Al	8	Alleluia Te martyrum candidatus laudat
	g02328	Al	8	Alleluia Isti sunt qui venerunt
	g00040	Al	1	Alleluia Mirabilis dominus noster
116r				
	g01322	Al	1	Alleluia Justi epulentur et exsultent
	g00325	Al	1	Alleluia Fulgebunt justi et tamquam
116v				
	g02217	Al	1	Alleluia Judicabunt sancti nationes et
	g00041	Al	2	Alleluia Sancti tui domine benedicent
117r				
	g00024	Al	4	Alleluia Gaudete justi in domino
	g00576	Of	2	Anima nostra sicut passer erepta
117v				
	g00116	Of	1	Laetamini in domino et exsultate
	g01317	Of	8	Mirabilis deus in sanctis suis
118r				
	g01323	Of	4	Exultabunt sancti in gloria laetabuntur
	g00244	Of	6	Gloriabuntur in te omnes qui
118v				
	g01309	Cm	1	Gaudete justi in domino alleluia
	g00209	Cm	3	Justorum animae in manu dei
119r				
	g00472	Cm	1	Posuerunt mortalia servorum tuorum domine
	g00695	Cm	1	Amen dico vobis quod uni

119v	g01324	Cm	8	Dico autem vobis amicis meis
Commune unius Confessoris et				
	g01271	In	1	Statuit ei dominus testamentum pacis
	g01271a.1	Inv	1	Misericordias domini in aeternum cantabo
	g01338	In	3	Sacerdotes tui domine induant justitiam
120r	g01338a	InV	3	Memento domine David et omnis
	g01280	In	6T	Sacerdotes dei benedicite dominum sancti
	g01280a	InV	6T	Benedicite omnia opera domini domino
	g02264	In	2T	Sacerdotes ejus induam salutare et
120v	g02264a	InV	2T	Memento domine David et omnis
	g01349	In	6	Os justi meditabitur sapientiam et
	g01349a	InV	6	Noli aemulari in malignantibus
	g01332	Gr	5	Ecce sacerdos magnus qui in
121r	g01332a	GrV	5	Non est inventus similis illi
	g02035	Gr	3	Juravit dominus et non paenitebit
	g02035a	GrV	3	Dixit dominus domino meo sede
121v	g01272	Gr	1	Inveni David servum meum
	g01272a	GrV	1	Nihil proficiet inimicus in eo
122r	g01339	Gr	1	Sacerdotes ejus induam salutare
	g01339a	GrV	1	Illuc producam cornu David
122v	g01360	Gr	1	Domine praevenisti eum in benedictionibus
	g01360a	GrV	1	Vitam petiit et tribuisti ei
	g01343	Gr	1	Os justi meditabitur sapientiam
123r	g01343a	GrV	1	Lex dei ejus in corde
	g00226	Al	2	Alleluia Inveni David servum meum
123v	g01346	Al	1	Alleluia Justus germinabit sicut liliu
	g02657	Al	2	Alleluia Os justi meditabitur sapientiam
124r	g01288	Of	8	Inveni David servum meum oleo
	g01278	Of	2	Veritas mea et misericordia mea
	g01363	Of	6	Desiderium animae ejus tribuisti ei
124v	g01354	Cm	3T	Beatus servus quem cum venerit
	g00012	Cm	7	Domine quinque talenta tradidisti
125r	g00318	Cm	7	Fidelis servus et prudens quem
	g01279	Cm	4	Semel juravi in sancto meo
125v	In commun. Unius virginis			
	501004	In	1	Gaudeamus omnes in domino
	501004a	InV	1	Eructavit cor meum verbum bonum

126r				
	g01380	In	8	Dilexisti justitiam et odisti iniquitatem
	g01380a	InV	8	Eruclavit cor meum verbum bonum
	g00363	In	5	Loquebar de testimoniis tuis
126v				
	g00363a	InV	5	Beati immaculati in via qui
	g01390	In	2	Vultum tuum deprecabuntur omnes divites
	g01390a	InV	2	Eruclavit cor meum
	g01366	Gr	8	Dilexisti justitiam et odisti iniquitatem
127r				
	g01366c	GrV	8	Propterea unxit te Deus
	g01381	Gr	5	Specie tua et pulchritudine tua
	g01381c	GrV	5	Propter veritatem et mansuetudinem et
127v				
	g01374	Gr ²⁸	5	Adjuvabit eam deus vultu suo
	g01374a	GrV	5	Fluminis impetus laetificat civitatem dei
128r				
	g00412	Gr	5	Propter veritatem et mansuetudinem et
	g00412a	GrV	5	Audi filia et vide et
128v				
	g02713	Al	1	Alleluia Aemulor enim vos dei
	g02265	Al	1	Alleluia Veni electa mea et
129r				
	g01383	Al	1	Alleluia Adducentur regi virgines post
	g00083	Of	3	Offerentur regi virgines post eam
129v				
	g01388	Of	8	Filiae regum in honore tuo
	g01378	Of	8	Diffusa est gratia in labiis
130r				
	g01883	Cm	8	Simile est regnum caelorum homini
	g00302	Cm	6	Diffusa est gratia in labiis
130v				
	g01379	Cm	4	Feci iudicium et justitiam domine
	g01389	Cm	5	Quinque prudentes virgines acceperunt oleum
	g00517	Gr	2T	In sole posuit tabernaculum suum
131r				
De sancto spiritu				
	g01090	In		Spiritus domini*
	g01217	Gr		Beata gens*
	g01092	Al		Alleluia Veni sancte*
	g01094	Of		Confirma hoc*
	g01095	Cm		Factus est*
De sancto spiritu infra septuag.				
	g00789	In		Dum sanctificatus*
De Sancta Cruce				
	g00180	In		Nos autem*
	505005	Gr		Christus factus est*
	g00182	Al		Alleluia Dulce lignum*
	g00376	Of		Protege domine*

²⁸ Fols. 127v–128r graduale marked as responsorium.

g02068	Cm		Per lignum*
Commem. Marie			
501007	In		Rorate caeli*
g00517	Gr	2T	In sole posuit tabernaculum suum
g00517a	GrV	2T	A summo caelo egressio ejus
131v			
507002	Al	8	Alleluia Virga Jesse floruit virgo ²⁹

Lutheran Gradual in Swedish

132r–133r³⁰

[Nativitas Domini]

V Christus är födder aff en iunffru reen (without notation)
 Sq 5 Alle Christene frögda sig³¹

133r–134r

[Dom. Resurrectionis]

V Christus är upstonden aff dödha (without notation)
 Sq 1 [J]esus Christus han är wårdhen³²

134v

Empty red staves

135r

[In summis festis]

K 48 Ky [H]erre forbarma tigh offuer oss
 mMELO48
 G 56 Gl Ære wari Gudh I högdenne
 mBOS056

136r

S 203 Sa Helig. Helig. Helig Herren Gudh
 mTHA203
 A 114 Ag O Gudz Lamb som
 mSCB114
 BD Tackom och loffuom

136v

[De sancto spiritu]

K 96 Ky Herre forbarma tigh offuer oss
 mMELO96
 G 24 Gl Ære wari Gudh I högdenne
 mBOS24

137r

S 116 Sa Helig. Helig. Helig Herren Gudh³³
 mTHA116

137v

A 138 Ag O Gudz Lamb som
 mSCB138

[In simplicibus]

²⁹ The unfinished temporal section and the Comm. Marie feast end here.

³⁰ Originally only with empty red staves. Keskiaho 2017.

³¹ Lat. *Laetabundus exsultet fidelis*

³² Lat. *Victimae paschali laudes*.

³³ The Finnish words of the chant “Pyhä, pyhä, pyhä, etc.” are also written between the notes and the Swedish text.

138r	K 58 mMELO58	Ky	Herre forbarma tigh offuer oss
	G 51 mBOS51	Gl	Ære wari Gudh I högdenne
138v	S 223 mTHA223	Sa	Helig. Helig. Helig Herren Gudh
	A 209 mSCB209	Ag	O Gudz Lamb som
139r	[Tempore paschali]		
	K 39 mMELO39	Ky	Herre forbarma tigh offuer oss
	G 12 mBOS12	Gl	Ære wari Gudh I högdenne
140r		BD	Gwdh wari tack och loff, Alleluija Alleluija Alleluija.
	[Dom. Pentecostes]		
		Sq	Pyhen hengen armo olcon ... O pyhe wirgottaya. Sine [...] ³⁴

Kyriale

Fols, 141r–150v, ordinarium missae

141r	[In summis festis] ³⁵		
	509501 mMELO48	Ky	Kyrie eleison
141r–v	509502 mBOS056	Gl	Gloria in excelsis
141v–142r	509504 mTHA203	Sa	Sanctus sanctus sanctus dominus deus
142r	509505 mSCB114	Ag	Agnus dei qui tollis peccata
142r–v	[In festis duplicibus]		
	509501 mMELO18	Ky	Kyrie eleison
142v	509502 mBOS056	Gl	Gloria in excelsis*

³⁴ Lat. *Sancti spiritus adsit nobis gratia*. Defective at the end. Keskiaho 2017.

³⁵ There are no indications for the use of the series in the manuscript. The uses are defined by Ermo Äikää (1995, 70–72).

142v	509504 Sa mTHA49	Sanctus sanctus sanctus dominus deus
142v–143r	509505 Ag mSCB136	Agnus dei qui tollis peccata
143r	[Tempore paschali] 509501 Ky mMELO39	Kyrie eleison
143r–v	509502 Gl mBOS12	Gloria in excelsis
144r	[De sancto spiritu] 509501 Ky mMELO96	Kyrie eleison
144r–v	509502 Gl mBOS24	Gloria in excelsis
145r	509504 Sa mTHA116	Sanctus sanctus sanctus dominus deus
145r	509505 Ag mSCB138	Agnus dei qui tollis peccata
145v	[In sabbatis quando fit de beata virgine & De beata virgine feriae; De beata virgine Solemne] 509501 Ky mMELO171	Kyrie eleison
145v–146v	509502 Gl mBOS23	Gloria in excelsis ... Spiritus et alme orphanorum ³⁶
146v–147v	509502 Gl mBOS51a	Gloria in excelsis ... Per precem ³⁷
147v	509504 Sa mTHA19	Sanctus sanctus sanctus dominus deus ... Benedictus Marie filius ³⁸
148r	509505 Ag mSCB37	Agnus dei qui tollis peccata
148r	[In semiduplicibus] 509501 Ky mMELO68	Kyrie eleison

³⁶ Gloria trope. See, Äikää 1995, 99–100 and Hiley 1995, 161.

³⁷ Gloria trope. See, Äikää 1995, 100.

³⁸ Sanctus interpolation. See, Äikää 1995, 85.

148r–149r	509502	Gl	Gloria in excelsis
	mBOS19		
149r	509504	Sa	Sanctus sanctus sanctus dominus deus
	mTHA32		
149r–v	509505	Ag	Agnus dei qui tollis peccata
	mSCB226		
149v	[In dominicus diebus et in simplicibus festis]		
	509501	Ky	Kyrie eleison
	mMELO58		
149v–150r	509502	Gl	Gloria in excelsis
	mBOS51		
150r–v	509504	Sa	Sanctus sanctus sanctus dominus deus
	mTHA223		
150v	509505	Ag	Agnus dei qui tollis peccata
	mSCB209		

Sequentiarium

151r–195v; sequentiarium; (177v–178v; three blank folios)

151r–v	[Nativitas Domini]		
	508017	Sq 6	Laetabundus exsultet fidelis
151v–152r	[Dom. Resurrectionis] In die pasche et duobus diebus		
	ah54007	Sq 1	Victimae paschali laudes
152r–153v	Ascensio Domini		
	ah54152	Sq 1	Omnes gentes plaudite festos choros ducite
153v–154v	Dom. Pentecostes		
	ah53070	Sq 7	Sancti spiritus adsit nobis gratia
155r–v	Fer. 2 Pent.		
	850303	Sq 1	Veni sancte spiritus et emitte
155v–157r	In festo sancte trinitatis		
	ah54161	Sq 7	Profitentes unitatem veneremur trinitatem
157r–159r	Corporis Christi		
	ah50385	Sq 7	Lauda Sion salvatorem lauda ducem
	ah54196	Sq 7	Lauda sponsa genitricem ³⁹

³⁹ The text is copied below the *Lauda Sion salvatorem* sequence text.

159r–160v				
In Dedicacione Eccl. In die consecracionis et anniversariis dedicacionibus ecclesie				
ah55031	Sq	1	Rex Salomon fecit templum quorum	
160v–161v				
De sancto Henrico				
g04537	Sq	5	Coetus noster laetus esto	
161v–				
de compassione beata Maria virgins sequ.				
ah08059	Sq	1	Stabat iuxta Christi crucem	
162r–163r				
Inventio Crucis				
ah54129	Sq	1	Veneremur crucis lignum	
163r–164r				
Erici				
g04538	Sq	4T	Gratulemur dulci prosa	
Joannis Baptistae				
ah55179	Sq	4T	Precursorem summi regis et praeconem ⁴⁰	
164v–165r				
Eskilli				
–	Sq	4T	Hac in die gloriemur	
165r–166r				
Petri, Pauli				
ah42312	Sq	7	Iubar mundo geminatur	
166r–167v				
Margaritae				
–	Sq	1	Odas summo regi Christo	
[Catharinae]				
ah08213	Sq	1	Odas in hac die letas ⁴¹	
168r–169r				
Mariae Magdalenae				
ah08230	Sq	8	Monti Syon dat virorem	
169r–170v				
Olavi				
ah42302	Sq	7	Lux illuxit letabunda	
170v–171v				
Laurentii				
ah54061	Sq	7	Stola iocunditatis alleluia	
171v–172v				
Assumptio Mariae				
ah54245	Sq	7	Salve mater salvatoris	
172v–174r				
ah53104	Sq		Congaudent angelorum chori gloriosae ⁴²	
174r–175r				
Augustini				
ah55075	Sq	8	De profundis tenebrarum mundo lumen ⁴³	

⁴⁰ The text is copied below the *Gratulemur dulci prosa* sequence text.

⁴¹ The text is copied below the *Odas summo regi Christo* sequence text.

⁴² Empty staves.

⁴³ The melody is copied only from the beginning of the sequence to the *Leges sacrae*.

175r–176r
Nativitas Mariae
ah54188 Sq 1 Nativitas Marie virginis que nos lavit
176r–177r
Michaelis
ah55258 Sq Laus erumpat ex affectu⁴⁴ ... erunt ordinum distinctae [gloriae justis...]
177v–178v Empty
179r–180r
[Omnium Sanctorum]
ah55037 Sq 8 Superne matris gaudia
180r–181r
Martini
ah53181 Sq Sacerdotem Christi Martinum
181v–183r
[Nicolai episcopi]
g04543 Sq 6 Felix urbs est paterea
182r–183r
De sancta Anna
Sq Sq Sanctae Annae sonorus
183r–184v
[In festo patronum regni Sveciae]
– Sq 7 Exultant angelorum chori
184v–185v
[unius martiris et pontifices]
– Sq Gaude martir gloriose milesque
185v–186r
[De uno confessore et pont.]
– Sq 4T Ave gemma praesulum sacerdotum
186v, 194v, 194r, 193v⁴⁵
De domina nostra
ah54057 Sq [A]ve preclara maris stella
186v: Ave preclara maris stella ... Tu agnum regem terrae
194v: dominatorem inoabitici ... ora virgo nos illo
194r: pane caeli dignos effici ... valeat mens intelligere /
193v: Christus perianismi fidem ... saeculi ad te auctor transire. Amen.
187r
[Pro defunctis]
ah54178 Sq 2 [Dies irae...] Inter oves locum praesta, ... requiem sempiternam. Amen.
187r–v
De martiribus
ah55014 Sq 2 [O] beata beatorum martirum solemnina
188r (bound upside down in reverse order)
[Pro defunctis]
ah54178 Sq 2 [Dies irae... cum] vix justus sit securus ... ne perenni cremer igne.
188v (bound upside down in reverse order)
[Divisio Apostolorum]
ah50267 Sq [Caeli enarrant gloriam dei et ...] pacis ut ... rex in caelis. Amen.

⁴⁴ Empty staves. Also, a part of the text is missing.

⁴⁵ The leaves are bound in the incorrect order.

[Pro defunctis]

ah54178 Sq 2 Dies irae dies illa ... Quem patronum rogaturus, cum⁴⁶

189r (bound upside down in reverse order)

ah50267 Sq [Caeli enarrant gloriam dei et ...] Sanguine Christi ... indivisum
et in vinculo

189v (bound upside down in reverse order)

ah50267 Sq [Caeli enarrant gloriam dei et ...] me pater ... praedicantium pacem

190r (bound upside down in reverse order)

ah50267 Sq [Caeli enarrant gloriam dei et ...] facti de terra caeli ... Sicut misit

190v (bound upside down in reverse order)

[Divisio Apostolorum]

ah50267 Sq Caeli enarrant gloriam dei et ... incarnati [facti de terra ...]

ah54216 Sq 5T [Ave maria gratia ... sine spina] genetrix es facta ... per saecula. Amen.

191r (bound upside down in reverse order)

[Annuntiatio Mariae]

ah54216 Sq 5T [A]ve maria gratia plena ... sine spina [genetrix ...

191v (bound upside down in reverse order, empty staves)

ah55007 Sq [Jucundare plebs... sacri]-ficatur leo mortem... ab imo superius.

192r (bound upside down in reverse order, empty staves)

ah55007 Sq [Jucundare plebs ... deo sicut] descendit ... vitulus sacri-[ficatur...]

192v (bound upside down in reverse order, empty staves)

ah55007 Sq [Jucundare plebs ...] ipsi scribens ...de deo sicut [descendit ...]

193r (bound upside down in reverse order)

De evangelistis

ah55007 Sq Jucundare plebs fidelis ... Est Joannes testis [ipsi ...]

ah54087 Sq [Qui sunt isti qui volant ... matrem ecclesiam] Adhuc sunt ...Amen.

193v

Andreae

ah54087 Sq Qui sunt isti qui volant ... matrem ecclesiam [Adhuc sunt ...]

ah54057 Sq [Ave preclara maris stella] Christus perianismi ... transire. Amen.

194r

ah54057 Sq [Ave preclara maris stella...] pane caeli dignos ... mens intelligere

194v

ah54057 Sq [Ave preclara maris stella...] dominatorem inoabitici ... virgo nos illo

⁴⁶ The incipit of the Finnish sequence “Sanoi pietar domio päiwän wihan” is written beneath the Latin text.

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